

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERISATION OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED MoNiCr-316L MATERIALS BY DED-LB/W FOR ENERGY APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

This paper deals with the development and characterisation of functionally graded MoNiCr-316L materials manufactured by directed energy deposition with laser beam and wire feedstock (DED-LB/W). The work verifies the feasibility of joining a nickel-based MoNiCr alloy, developed by COMTES FHT a.s. for high-temperature molten-salt applications, with austenitic stainless steel 316L. Cubic blocks of 20 x 20 x 20 mm were produced in two deposition sequences: MoNiCr deposited on 316L and 316L deposited on MoNiCr. The samples were evaluated in the as-built state and after heat treatment at 1100 °C and 1200 °C, as well as after hot isostatic pressing at 1200 °C and 150 MPa. The interface was assessed by metallography, EDS line analysis and HV1 hardness profiling. The results show that the deposition sequence has a decisive effect on interface morphology. Deposition of MoNiCr on 316L produced a sharply defined transition, whereas deposition of 316L on MoNiCr resulted in a wider mixed zone. This behaviour is attributed to the lower solidus and liquidus temperatures of MoNiCr and to local remelting during subsequent deposition. Heat treatment and HIP promoted recrystallisation and reduced hardness gradients across the interface. The results confirm that DED-LB/W enables stable MoNiCr-316L multimaterial structures with an interface that can be tailored by deposition order and post-processing.

Keywords: Functionally graded materials, MoNiCr nickel alloy, 316L stainless steel, DED-LB/W, heat treatment

1. INTRODUCTION

Functionally graded metallic materials are attractive for components whose local service conditions require different combinations of cost, corrosion resistance, strength and thermal stability. Additive manufacturing, particularly directed energy deposition (DED), enables such materials to be produced by changing the feedstock during the build and by locally controlling the melt pool and dilution conditions [1-3]. This capability is relevant for energy components, repairs and claddings, where a structural body may be made from a widely available steel while only the surface or functional region contains a more expensive corrosion-resistant alloy.

Most current knowledge on metallic FGMs produced by DED has been developed on stainless steel-to-Inconel systems, especially 304L/IN625, 316L/IN625 and 316L/IN718. These studies show that apparently simple material transitions are controlled by local solidification path, remelting, dilution, segregation and secondary-phase formation [4-7]. The order of deposition is also important, because the thermal cycle imposed by the second material can change the extent of interfacial remelting and therefore the width and chemistry of the transition zone [8].

The present study extends this concept to the MoNiCr-316L system. MoNiCr is a nickel-molybdenum-chromium alloy developed for demanding energy applications involving high temperatures and molten fluoride salts. Previous work demonstrated that the alloy can be processed by DED-LB/P after optimisation of chemistry and feedstock quality [9], and its composition is relevant to corrosion-resistant materials considered for molten salt reactor environments [10,11]. The aim of this paper is to evaluate whether DED-LB/W can produce a metallurgically sound MoNiCr-316L transition and how deposition order and post-processing affect the interface, microstructure and hardness distribution.

2. EXPERIMENTAL MATERIAL AND METHODS

Additive manufacturing using the directed energy deposition method DED-LB/W (Directed Energy Deposition) was carried out on a Meltio system equipped with a 6-axis Fanuc robotic arm. The system employs a total laser power of up to 1200 W delivered by six 200 W fiber lasers with a wavelength of 976 nm. The machine operates in a 6+2 axis configuration and offers a working envelope of 600 × 600 × 1000 mm, while enabling the processing of rotational components with a length of up to 2000 mm. The technology supports multimaterial deposition using two wires that can be switched during the process and incorporates electrical wire preheating. Typical process parameters include a layer height of 0.5–1.2 mm, a deposition rate of approximately 350 g/h when processing steel, and the use of wire with a diameter of 0.8–1.2 mm.

Functionally graded blocks with dimensions of 20 x 20 x 20 mm were produced by DED-LB/W, Figure 1. One half of each block was manufactured from commercially available 316L stainless steel wire with a diameter of 1.0 mm and the other half from optimised MoNiCr wire with a diameter of 1.05 mm. The chemical composition of the MoNiCr alloy is shown in Table 1

Table 1 Chemical composition – MoNiCr (wt.%)

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Fe	Mo	Cu	Al	Ti	V	W	Nb	B	N	O	Ni
<0.001	0.19	0.18	<0.003	<0.003	5.8	2.3	16.88	0.002	0.23	0.008	0.019	0.08	0.02	0.001	0.0025	0.0012	73.19

Figure 1 Functionally graded blocks

Table 1 DED-LB/W process parameters for the graded MoNiCr-316L blocks

Parameter	316L	MoNiCr
Layer height (mm)	1.2	1.2
Wire diameter (mm)	1.0	1.05
Track spacing (mm)	1.0	1.0
Travel speed (mm/s)	10.0	8.0
Wire feed speed (mm/s)	14.6	10.16
Laser power (W)	750	950
Argon flow rate (l/min)	10	10
Build strategy	zig-zag infill +90°	zig-zag infill +90°

Two deposition sequences were investigated. In the first sequence, 316L was deposited first and MoNiCr was deposited on top of it; this variant is denoted as 1_316L-MoNiCr. In the second sequence, MoNiCr was deposited first and 316L was deposited on top of it; this variant is denoted as 2_MoNiCr-316L. Four blocks were manufactured for each sequence. The samples were evaluated in the as-built condition and after heat treatment at 1100 °C for 1 h with nitrogen gas cooling, heat treatment at 1200 °C for 1 h with nitrogen gas cooling, and HIP at 1200 °C for 1 h under 150 MPa followed by rapid argon cooling. Hot isostatic pressing (HIP) was carried out at the Centrum výzkumu Řež using a QIH 21 – Molybdenum URQ unit manufactured by the Swedish company Quintus Technologies AB. The furnace operates in a protective argon atmosphere with a maximum operating temperature of 1,400 °C and a maximum pressure of up to 207 MPa.

Metallographic specimens were prepared by sequential grinding followed by polishing according to standard metallographic procedures, with the final polishing step performed using OP-S Non-Dry colloidal silica

suspension (0.25 μm). Sample preparation was carried out on a Tegamin 30 system (Struers GmbH, Ballerup, Denmark). Microstructural features were revealed using a Kalling's etchant. Optical metallographic observations were conducted using a Nikon Eclipse MA200 light microscope (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with NIS-Elements 5.2 digital image acquisition and analysis software. Detailed microstructural characterization was subsequently performed using a JEOL IT-500HR scanning electron microscope (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) coupled with an energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS Octane Elite Super) along the interface regions, which enabled line analyses of Mo, Cr, Fe and Ni across the transition zone. Vickers microhardness profiles (HV1) were measured using an automated Durascan microhardness tester to evaluate hardness variations in both base materials and in the interface region.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Interface morphology and chemical mixing

The as-built samples revealed a clear influence of deposition order. When 316L was deposited first and MoNiCr was deposited subsequently, the transition between the two alloys remained relatively sharp, **Figure 2**. In contrast, when MoNiCr was deposited first and the subsequent layers were made from 316L, the interface became less abrupt and a broader mixed zone was formed, **Figure 3**.

Figure 2 1_316L-MoNiCr

Figure 3 2_MoNiCr-316L

The EDS line analysis confirmed this qualitative observation: sample 1_316L-MoNiCr (**Figure 4**) showed an abrupt change in Mo, Cr, Fe and Ni contents, whereas sample 2_MoNiCr-316L (**Figure 5**) showed a smoother chemical transition and higher local mixing in the melt pool.

Figure 4 EDS line analysis 1_316L-MoNiCr**Figure 5** EDS line analysis 2_ MoNiCr-316L

The different response can be explained by the difference in melting ranges. The MoNiCr alloy has a lower solidus, approximately 1260 °C, and a liquidus in the range of approximately 1340-1370 °C. The 316L steel has a narrower and higher melting range, with a solidus of approximately 1370-1400 °C and a liquidus of approximately 1400-1450 °C. Therefore, deposition of 316L on MoNiCr more easily remelts the MoNiCr surface and promotes dilution, while deposition of MoNiCr on 316L leads to a more clearly defined transition.

3.2 Microstructure after post-processing

Outside the transition zone, both materials in the as-built state contained elongated and relatively coarse grains oriented along the build direction, which is typical for DED materials solidified under a strong thermal gradient, **Figure 6** and **Figure 7**. After heat treatment at 1100 °C and 1200 °C, the microstructure changed to recrystallised grains with annealing twins, and the traces of the original melt pools became much less visible. This indicates that post-processing was effective in reducing the strongly directional as-built microstructure and in stabilising the multimaterial transition.

Figure 7 Microstructure of MoNiCr

3.3 Hardness distribution

The hardness results are summarised in **Table 2**. In the as-built condition, the 316L regions showed the highest hardness, especially in the 2_ MoNiCr-316L sequence, where the average 316L hardness reached 209 HV1. The transition region had 176 HV1 in the 1_316L-MoNiCr sequence and 152 HV1 in the 2_ MoNiCr-316L sequence. After heat treatment and HIP, the hardness of the 316L region decreased markedly, while the MoNiCr region remained in a narrower range of approximately 157-163 HV1. The interface hardness after

post-processing converged to approximately 140-149 HV1, indicating that the initial hardness gradients were largely reduced.

Table 2 Average HV1 hardness of the graded MoNiCr-316L samples

Condition	Interface (HV1)	316L (HV1)	MoNiCr (HV1)
1 316L-MoNiCr, as-built	176	193	174
2 MoNiCr-316L, as-built	152	209	169
1 316L-MoNiCr, 1100 °C	146	133	159
2 MoNiCr-316L, 1100 °C	149	131	163
1 316L-MoNiCr, 1200 °C	140	133	160
2 MoNiCr-316L, 1200 °C	146	124	161
1 316L-MoNiCr, HIP	147	130	162
2 MoNiCr-316L, HIP	146	132	157

Note: HIP was performed at 1200 °C for 1 h under 150 MPa.

4. DISCUSSION

The results show that the MoNiCr-316L interface is not determined only by the nominal alloy pair, but also by the thermal and metallurgical sequence of deposition. This agrees with previous work on steel-to-nickel alloy transitions, where melt-pool remelting, dilution and deposition sequence were found to control the interface geometry and local mechanical response [4,7,8]. For the present material pair, the wider transition observed after deposition of 316L on MoNiCr is consistent with the lower melting range of MoNiCr. The incoming 316L layer is deposited at a temperature high enough to partially remelt the MoNiCr surface, resulting in a chemically broader transition zone. Conversely, the deposition of MoNiCr on 316L is less effective in remelting the higher-melting 316L substrate, leading to a sharper transition.

From a component design perspective, additive manufacturing provides a unique advantage by enabling the character of the material transition to be actively tailored through the choice of deposition sequence. An appropriate deposition order allows the expensive MoNiCr alloy to be strategically placed only in clearly defined functional regions of the component, for example as a corrosion-resistant surface or lining, while the remaining volume can be manufactured from a more economical material.

The heat treatment response is particularly important for practical application. The as-built DED microstructure is strongly directional, and the different local thermal histories of 316L, MoNiCr and the transition zone produce non-uniform hardness. After heat treatment or HIP, recrystallisation and partial homogenisation reduce the hardness contrast between the individual regions. Similar effects of post-processing have been reported for other stainless steel-to-nickel alloy FGMs, where heat treatment changes the local microstructure and hardness profile along the compositional path [6,7]. In the present case, the convergence of interface hardness to approximately 140-149 HV1 indicates that the post-processing route is effective for stabilising the mechanical response of the multimaterial block.

The main application significance of the MoNiCr-316L system lies in the possibility of combining a relatively low-cost, well-established stainless steel with a nickel-based alloy developed for aggressive high-temperature environments. This is relevant for energy components, repairs and local claddings, where only selected regions require high corrosion resistance or high-temperature stability. Previous studies of Ni-Mo-Cr alloys for molten salt systems show that corrosion performance is controlled not only by chemical composition but also by microstructure and second-phase content [10]. The ability to manufacture a stable 316L/MoNiCr transition by DED-LB/W therefore represents an important step towards functionally tailored parts for advanced energy systems. Nevertheless, long-term stability of the interface under thermal cycling, mechanical loading and exposure to molten salts remains to be verified.

5. CONCLUSION

Functionally graded MoNiCr-316L blocks were successfully produced by DED-LB/W in two deposition sequences. The main conclusions are as follows:

- Deposition order had a decisive influence on interface morphology. Deposition of MoNiCr on 316L produced a sharper transition, while deposition of 316L on MoNiCr produced a broader mixed zone due to stronger remelting of the lower-melting MoNiCr surface.
- EDS line analysis confirmed the difference in chemical mixing. The 2_MoNiCr-316L sequence showed a smoother transition of Mo, Cr, Fe and Ni across the interface than the 1_316L-MoNiCr sequence.
- The as-built microstructure contained elongated grains aligned with the build direction. Heat treatment at 1100 °C and 1200 °C promoted recrystallisation and reduced the visibility of the original melt-pool structure.
- Post-processing reduced the hardness gradients across the multimaterial structure. Interface hardness converged from 176 and 152 HV1 in the as-built state to approximately 140-149 HV1 after heat treatment or HIP.
- The 316L-MoNiCr combination is technologically suitable for DED-LB/W and offers a promising route for locally tailored components in energy applications, where corrosion-resistant MoNiCr can be used only in functional regions while 316L forms the supporting body.

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